

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF MODULE IN COMBINATORICS AND PROBABILITY FOR GRADE 10 LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop and validate a module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. Existing problems from the Department of Education's current curriculum, such as the lack of teaching resources and learning materials for Combinatorics and Probability and the recorded low mean percentage score in the subject, made the researcher conceptualize the development of a module in Combinatorics and Probability. The development and validation of the module in Combinatorics and Probability for grade 10 learners adapted and utilized the ADDIE model, which consists of five steps, namely: (1) Analysis, (2) Design, (3) Development, (4) Implementation, and (5) Evaluation. The module was developed in terms of the objectives of each lesson, essential content, language used, and assessment and evaluation activities. The developed module was distributed to the mathematics teachers and master teachers, who assess and evaluate the validity of the module using four criteria: development of the objectives of each lesson, selection of essential content, selection of the language used, and development of the assessment and evaluation activities. The validation result revealed that the developed module is very much valid. The validated module was pilot-tested among 30 students whose academic performance was determined in terms of knowledge acquisition using pretest-posttest result analysis. Positive learning was determined based on the mean percentage score of the students' pretest and posttest with the net gain of 46.40 which shows that the learners' performance in the subject significantly improved obtaining outstanding (87%) and very satisfactory (13%) rating in the posttest. The mean score of the pilot-tested is 44.87. In general, the developed module is a potential learning material that will provide teachers and learners with what is needed for the teaching and learning process and will enhance the mathematical skills of grade 10 learners in Combinatorics and Probability.

Keywords: *Combinatorics, Content, Design, Development, Modular Instruction, Module, Probability, Validation, Validators*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics subject is a fundamental part of the school curriculum. This subject is an instrument for the development of all other sciences. Mathematics is all around us. Knowingly and unknowingly, we use Mathematics in our everyday lives (Gafoor et al, 2015). Mathematics provides us with an effective way of building mental discipline and encourages logical reasoning and mental rigor. In addition, mathematical concepts and knowledge play a significant role in better understanding other subjects such as Science, Social studies, and even Music and Arts (International Mathematical Union, 2020). Students' performance in Mathematics is consistently given attention in different countries because it is regarded as a main subject, which is significant for the growth and development of the nation. Capuno et al (2019) noted that Mathematics is challenging for Filipino students.

Even before the pandemic in 2020, the Philippines faced challenges in mathematics education. The Philippines has consistently performed poorly in international mathematics large-scale assessments. One of the tools used to gauge the quality of education worldwide is the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) conducts PISA every three years to assess the Mathematics, Science, and Reading knowledge and skills of 15-year-old students worldwide. Results of 2018 showed that the Philippines ranked the second lowest in Science and Mathematics among 79 countries. PISA results revealed that the Philippines obtained an average score of 353 in mathematics. The survey suggested interventions should be made with students from countries like the Philippines (CNN Philippines, 2019). The Department of Education states that with the PISA results reflecting learners' performance in the National Achievement Test, there is urgency in addressing issues and gaps in attaining the quality of education in the Philippines (DepEd, 2019).

The COVID-19 pandemic over the last two years has exacerbated the current education crisis and widened the learning gap in Mathematics among young students (Sooknanan and Seemungal, 2023). The situation led to a decline in math learning, as students may need more remediation to progress to new lessons, leading to learning gaps (Torres, 2021).

The Department of Education (DepEd) said that the Philippines' poor showing in the 2022 PISA indicates a five-to-six-year lag in learning competencies in the country. The Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally in the student assessment conducted by the OECD for 15-year-old learners. In the 2022 student assessment, the country scored approximately 120 points lower than the average scores, with 355 in Math, 347 in Reading, and 356 in Science.

Combinatorics is a field of Mathematics concerned with the problems of selection, arrangement, and operation within a finite or discrete system (Grunbaum et al, 2024). Combinatorics is an initial material about probability consisting of basic rules of counting, permutation, and combination. Probability is a beneficial concept in everyday life as it is essential in decision-making (Meika et al, 2018). At a higher level, permutation and combination materials are essential in learning discrete Mathematics (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2020). Moreover, NCTM states that combinatorics is essential as it is an integral part of the Mathematics curriculum from elementary to high school (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2020). Using the basic rules of calculation, permutations, and the right combinations of problem-solving skills is challenging. This is in line with Wraughton and Nolan (2012), who state that understanding the rules of counting is challenging for students, especially when they struggle to determine when and how to apply rules of multiplication, permutation, and combinations in calculation.

According to Mashiach et al (2004), combinatorics is a mathematical topic considered challenging to teach and learn. Also, according to Spiegelhalter (2011), probability is unintuitive and difficult. There are mathematical problems that introduce the idea that uncertainty is something that can be discussed and analyzed. One way to overcome such challenges in learning combinatorics and probability is to present the combinatorics problem from daily life. In studying permutations and combinations, students need a relevant real-world context to stimulate learning and knowledge (Busadееa et al, 2013). Along with this, Sukoriyanto et al (2016) stated that permutation and combination materials require problems in the form of real-world issues to retain their knowledge.

The lack of teaching resources and learning materials for Combinatorics and Probability and the low mean percentage score of the third quarterly assessment in the subject mentioned above were the reasons which made the researcher conceptualize the development of a module in Combinatorics and Probability. The consolidated result of the third quarterly examination's Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of students in Gasan District for the last five years was recorded, which became one of the bases for the researcher to develop a module in Combinatorics and Probability. The third quarter MPS of Gasan District in Mathematics 10 for the last five years are as follows: 52.5 in 2019, 64.2 in 2020, 55.2 in 2021, 58.2 in 2022, and 56.89 in 2023. With these results, grade 10 learners are on the average level of mastery in Mathematics 10 in the third quarter.

Integrating Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) with alternative learning delivery modalities (LDMs) will help DepEd ensure that all learners have access to quality basic education, even those learners who cannot come to school every day because of financial issues. The development of instructional design and materials ensures that learners achieve specific learning goals or educational outcomes reflected in the education curriculum and provide relevant instructions suitable for a wide range of learning environments. According to the DepEd Secretary Leonor M. Briones, as stated by Malipot (2020), the SLMs and other LDMs are in place to address the needs of every learner. They cover all the bases to ensure that basic education is accessible.

Aside from the scarcity or lack of learning materials, there is a need to design and develop the material to help grade 10 learners understand the concept of Combinatorics and Probability. Thus, the researcher was encouraged and determined to develop a module.

The main purpose of this study is to develop and validate a module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. It focused on proving that Combinatorics and Probability in the third quarter for grade 10 can be taught significantly using instructional modules. Specifically, the topics included in the module are based on the Most Essential Competencies (MELCs), which include the following: Permutations of objects, Combinations of objects, Solving Problems on Permutations and Combinations, Probability of Compound Events, Union and Intersections of Events, and Solving Problems on Probability.

The researcher utilized the ADDIE model to design and develop the learning module. The ADDIE model is a structured and systematic approach that helps solve learning problems by tailoring the learning resources to meet students' needs and characteristics. This model comprises five stages: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation.

The module covered Combinatorics and Probability, which deals with selection, arrangement, and operation within a finite system (Torio et al, 2018) and was explicitly designed for Grade 10 students. On the other hand, the probability is the likelihood of something happening. When unsure about an event's outcome, we can discuss the probabilities of specific results and how probable they are. The probability of an event can only be from 0 to 1, and it can also be expressed as a percentage (Khan et al, 2020).

Significant research has been conducted on the development and validation of educational modules. However, further studies are needed to assess the effectiveness and benefits of module development on the curriculum. Thus, there is a need to adequately explore the development and validation of Mathematics lessons such as Combinatorics and Probability.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to develop a module in Combinatorics and Probability as an alternative delivery mode of instruction to reach Grade 10 learners.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How does the module in Combinatorics and Probability for grade 10 learners was developed in terms of:
 - 1.1 development of the intended learning outcomes,
 - 1.2 selection of the essential content,
 - 1.3 selection of the language used,
 - 1.4 development of the assessment and evaluation activities,

- 1.5 selection of references from available teaching and learning sources,
 - 1.6 time frame of development, and
 - 1.7 development of cover page and packaging?
2. What is the level of validity of the developed module as assessed by the Mathematics teachers and master teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 lesson's objectives,
 - 2.2 content,
 - 2.3 language used
 - 2.4 assessment and evaluation activities?
 3. What are the comments/feedback and suggestions of the experts/validators to help enhance the developed module in Combinatorics and Probability
 4. What enhanced module could be developed by the researcher based on the validation made by the respondents?
 5. What impact does the enhance module have on Grade 10 learners' knowledge acquisition performance, as assessed through pretest and posttest result analysis?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-evaluative research design, which focused on the know-how of developing and validating the module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners.

The ADDIE model was utilized to develop and validate the Combinatorics and Probability module for Grade 10 students. ADDIE means Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. The module's goals, target audience, and resources were analyzed in the analysis phase. In the design phase, essential content, objectives, and strategies aligned with the instructional goals were selected and designed. The development phase includes developing objectives, selecting essential content, determining the language used, and developing assessment and evaluation activities. In the implementation phase, the pre-crafted module was distributed to Mathematics teachers and master teachers for validation. In the evaluation phase, the module was assessed for developing lesson objectives, selecting essential content and language used, and developing assessment and evaluation activities. Each criterion has quantifying statements on which the evaluators based their assessment of the module.

This study utilized a survey questionnaire that included a 5-point Likert scale and checklist format. Content experts reviewed the collected data, and their suggestions were obtained through document analysis for further refinement of the module.

In the end, this study appraised the impact of the developed module in students' performance in Combinatorics and Probability topics in Grade 10 Quarter 3. The data was analyzed and interpreted using suitable statistical measures.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the province of Marinduque. This province belongs to the 81 provinces in the Philippine archipelago. Marinduque is considered the geographical center of the Philippines by the Luzon Datum of 1911, the mother of all Philippine geodetic surveys. The province is a "heart-shaped" island situated between Tayabas Bay and the Sibuyan Sea. Hence, the moniker "The Heart of the Philippines" was adopted. The province is located in the South Western Tagalog Region, also known as MIMAROPA, which was formerly designated as Region IV-B. The most widely accepted theory regarding the etymology of the province's name is that it is a hispanized corruption of either "malindig" or "malindug," which means "stand tall" or "elegant." This refers to the possibly active volcano in the island's southern section, Mount Malindig. The province of Marinduque comprises six (6) towns: Boac (the province's capital), Mogpog, Santa Cruz, Torrijos, Buenavista, and Gasan.

Specifically, this study was conducted among mathematics teachers and master teachers teaching mathematics 10 in the third quarter, combined with combinatorics and probability in the five (5) high schools in Gasan District. These include the following public high schools, as shown in Figure 3: Bangbang National High School, Bognuyan National High School, Paciano A. Sena Memorial High School, Tapuyan National High School, and Tiguion National High School.

Figure 3:
Map of Marinduque and Gasan Town

Research Population and Sample

The study's respondents were the Mathematics teachers and master teachers teaching grade 10 Mathematics. There are five (5) teacher-experts teaching Mathematics 10 in Gasan District, one teacher for each school. Participants are chosen on purpose because they are experts in the subject. Thus, the researcher employed purposive sampling to appraise the responses and data needed in the study holistically. Since the developed module caters to students studying Combinatorics and Probability, Grade 10 learners also constituted the population of the study which lasted for 9 weeks. The module was used by the 30 students of Bangbang National High School for further validation as well as to determine its effect on learners' performance.

Research Instrument

To interpret the level of validity of the developed module in Combinatorics and Probability, the researcher used the standardized Module Evaluation Checklist adapted from the study of scholars to develop and evaluate materials. The researcher utilized the questionnaire in checklist form used by Salazar (2018) to assess the content validity of the developed module in terms of objectives, essential content, language used, and assessment and evaluation activities.

The questionnaire consists of two (2) parts: (1) the participant's present status and qualifications and (2) the Evaluation Checklist for the Validity of the Developed Module. Part I of the questionnaire includes a demographic profile and workload profile, which gathered personal information about the teacher respondents, such as age, sex, civil status, length of service, area of specialization, civil service eligibility, current teaching position, subject taught, educational attainment, and professional training/seminar attended. Part II is the Evaluation Checklist for the validity of the developed module, which is divided into four (4) parts: (1) specific objectives of each lesson with five (5) listed characteristics of the objectives, (2) content of the module with ten (10) listed characteristics of the content, (3) language used with five (5) listed characteristics of the language used, and (4) assessment and evaluation activities with ten (10) listed characteristics of the assessment and evaluation activities. The evaluation checklist has five (5) degrees of intensity, with weights of five (5) being the highest rating and one (1) being the lowest rating. The scales of the statistical values adapted to assess the aspects are as follows:

Table 1.
Likert Scale for Evaluating Content Validity

Arbitrary Value	Weighted Mean	Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Excellent	Very Much Valid
4	3.40 – 4.19	Very Satisfactory	Much Valid
3	2.60 – 3.39	Satisfactory	Moderately Valid
2	1.80 – 2.59	Fair	Less Valid
1	1.00 – 1.79	Poor	Not Valid

The researcher devised pretest and posttest which were also validated by the mathematics teachers and master teachers. These tests are almost parallel and with the same difficulty level based on the contents of the module. Each item has four choices with which one is correct. Each test was administered in paper-pencil-test mode within a 60-minute period. The contents are also in consonance with the competencies specified in the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). The results of these tests were used to evaluate the effect of using the module to the learners' performance on the lessons of Combinatorics and Probability.

Data Gathering Procedure

Seeking Approval to Conduct the Study. First, the researcher sent a request letter to Dr. Lynn G. Mendoza, the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Marinduque, through the HR Office, asking permission to conduct the study in the five (5) public high schools in Gasan District through the distribution of survey questionnaires. The researcher also asked permission through a letter from Mr. Gueller Dee V. Salazar to adapt the instrument he used in his 2018 study to validate a developed module.

Administration and Retrieval of Questionnaires. Upon granting the researcher's request to adopt the research instrument used by Salazar (2018) and the approval of the Division Superintendent of Marinduque, the researcher printed a copy of the survey form and submitted it to the school district Supervisor of Gasan, Dr. Elvin C Perlas. The printed copy of the survey and consent forms were then personally distributed to the respondents. The researcher went to five (5) public high schools in Gasan District. These include the following public high schools: Bangbang National High School, Bognuyan National High School, Paciano A. Sena Memorial High School, Tapuyan National High School, and Tiguion National High School. The researcher gave the respondents one to two weeks to complete the questionnaire. Afterward, the researcher collected the completed survey questionnaires at the principal's respective office, and then the researcher consolidated the data. The researcher also did in-person interviews to validate the data gathered through the survey.

Collation, Organization, and Analysis of Data. After retrieving and collecting all the data needed, it was encoded, collated, organized, and statistically treated using the

appropriate statistical tools. Results were considered by the researcher in module revision and development.

Revision of the Developed Module in Combinatorics and Probability. After analyzing the respondents' results, comments, and suggestions, the study concluded that the developed module is very much valid. Based on the feedback received, the researcher revised certain parts of the module to transform it into a valuable learning resource for grade 10 students.

The final copy was implemented in the teaching-learning process using 30 students in Bangbang National High School. The researcher utilized the results of pretest and posttest administered to appraise the effect of the developed module to the learners' performance for the whole third quarter.

Statistical Treatment

The researcher statistically examined the collected data to provide answers to the study questions. The researcher recorded and tabulated the frequency of responses on the level of validity of the developed module in terms of the objectives of each lesson, essential content, the language used, and assessment and evaluation activities with which each category has quantifying statements.

The mean scores were computed to measure the respondent's evaluation of the developed module regarding the objectives of each lesson, essential content, language used, and assessment and evaluation activities.

The results of the evaluation of teachers and content experts to the instrument were coded on the 5-point Likert Scale determination per criterion, wherein the higher scores embody more positive responses. Scores were analyzed using a descriptive data analysis procedure. The scales of the statistical values adapted to assess the aspects are as follows:

Likert Scale for Evaluating Content Validity

Arbitrary Value	Weighted Mean	Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Excellent	Very Much Valid
4	3.40 – 4.19	Very Satisfactory	Much Valid
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2	1.80 – 2.59	Fair	Less Valid
1	1.00 – 1.79	Poor	Not Valid

RESULTS

Stages / Phases of Module Development

1. Development of the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) specify what learners are expected to know, understand, and be able to do as a result of an educational activity. These outcomes serve as a guide for the researcher in designing and developing the module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. Developing ILOs is a crucial step in crafting the module. They should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART).

First, the researcher defined the learning goals. The researcher began by clearly defining what the grade 10 learners of Gasan District should achieve by the end of the third quarter. The researcher considered the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) prescribed by the Department of Education (DepEd). These competencies were provided by DepEd for schools and teachers to use as the primary resource in choosing and implementing varied learning techniques and strategies appropriately.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has instructed schools to consult the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) when creating learning activity sheets, self-learning modules, and other instructional materials. Furthermore, schools are encouraged to adhere to the MELCs' content and to avoid creating new lists of learning competencies for different subject areas (Llego, 2023).

Table 2.

Most Essential Learning Competencies of Mathematics 10 Third Quarter

Quarter	Content Standards The learner...	Performance Standards The learner...	Most Essential Learning Competencies The learner...	Duration	K to 12 CG Code
Q3	demonstrates understanding of key concepts of combinatorics and probability	is able to use precise counting technique and probability in formulating conclusions and making decisions.	illustrates the permutation of objects.	Week 1 to 2	M10SP-IIIa-1
			solves problems involving permutations.		M10SP-IIIb-1
			illustrates the combination of objects.		M10SP-IIIc-1
			differentiates permutation from combination of n objects taken r at a time.	Week 3 to 4	M10SP-IIIc-2
			solves problems involving permutations and combinations.		Week 5
			illustrates events, and union and intersection of events.	Week 6	M10SP-IIIf-1

illustrates the probability of a union of two events.	Week 7	M10SP-IIIg-1
finds the probability of (AUB).	Week 8	M10SP-IIIg-h-1
illustrates mutually exclusive events.	Week 9	M10SP-IIIi-1
solves problems involving probability.		M10SP-IIIi-j-1

Table 2 above shows the Most Essential Learning Competencies of Mathematics 10 in the third quarter. These competencies are the intended learning outcomes which the researcher considered as a guide in designing and developing the module.

After identifying the learning goals/learning competencies, the researcher broke down the overarching goals into smaller, more manageable learning objectives, skills, or attitudes that learners should gain. The researcher ensures that each aim is aligned with the curriculum standards and overall goals and is achievable within the module's scope to be developed.

The study of Zalun (2023) revealed that the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) is highly utilized in terms of learning resources content validity, appropriateness of learners' activities, congruency of the lesson plan, alignment of the assessment, and time budget. It also revealed that the MELCs have a strong relationship with the level of learning development.

Next, the researcher applied Bloom's taxonomy to guide her in developing learning objectives. Bloom's taxonomy categorized learning objectives into six levels, ranging from simple recall of information to higher-order thinking skills such as evaluation and creation. The researcher ensured that learning objectives covered a range of cognitive levels to promote deep learning.

Each learning objective was expressed using precise, actionable verbs that describe observable behaviors. Action verbs such as analyze, evaluate, synthesize, and apply indicate the level of cognitive engagement required of learners. The vague and ambiguous language that can lead to confusion was avoided. The researcher reviewed the learning objectives to ensure that these are specific, clear, and unambiguous. Unnecessary jargon or complex language that may hinder understanding was removed. Each objective communicates precisely what learners are expected to accomplish. Also, learning objectives are sequenced logically, allowing for progression and coherence, starting from foundational concepts and skills to more advanced topics.

The researcher also considered the diverse needs and backgrounds of the learners when crafting learning objectives. The objectives are inclusive and accessible to all learners, regardless of their experience and prior knowledge.

Finally, the researcher reviewed the identified learning objectives multiple times to ensure they meet the learners' needs and align with the overall instructional goals. Based

on feedback from the teacher-respondents, the researcher revised parts of the objectives as needed.

2. Selection of the essential content

The researcher followed several steps in selecting the essential content of the module to be developed. The first step was to identify learning objectives. The researcher then clearly defined what the learners should achieve by the end of the third quarter.

The most important topics are determined for achieving the learning objectives. The researcher identified the core concepts and information essential for understanding the subject matter, which will be the module's focus. The topics/lessons under Mathematics 10 Combinatorics and Probability for Quarter 3 are listed per module every week, Module 1 to Module 10, with K to 12 curriculum guide codes. These are as follows:

- Module 1 – Week 1: Illustrating Permutations of Objects (M10SP-IIIa-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Permutation of Distinct Objects
 - Lesson 2: Illustrating Permutation of Non-Distinct Objects
 - Lesson 3: Illustrating Circular Permutation of Objects
- Module 2 – Week 2: Solving Problems involving Permutations of Objects (M10SP-IIIb-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving Problems involving Permutations of Objects
- Module 3 – Week 3: Illustrating Combinations of Objects (M10SP-IIIc-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Combinations of Objects
 - Lesson 2: Differentiating Permutation and Combination
- Module 4 – Week 4: Combination of n Objects Taken r at a Time (M10SP-IIIc-2)
 - Lesson 1: Combination of n objects taken r at a time
- Module 5 – Week 5: Solving Problems involving Permutations and Combinations (M10SP-IIId-e-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving Problems involving Permutations and Combinations
- Module 6 – Week 6: Events, and Union and Intersection of Events (M10SP-IIIf-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Different Types of Events
 - Lesson 2: Illustrating Union, and Intersection of Events
- Module 7 – Week 7: Probability of The Union of Two Events (M10SP-IIIg-1)
 - Lesson 1: Probability of The Union of Two Events
- Module 8 – Week 8: Solving the Probability of AUB (M10SP-IIIg-h-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving the Probability of AUB
- Module 9 – Week 9: Illustrating Mutually Exclusive Events (M10SP-IIIf-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Mutually Exclusive Events
- Module 10 – Week 10: Solving Problems involving Probabilities (M10SP-IIIj-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving the Probability of Independent Events and Dependent Events
 - Lesson 2: Solving Conditional Probability

Another important aspect considered by the researcher is the learners' needs. Understanding the background, prior knowledge, and learning preferences of the grade 10 learners of Gasan District is considered. It is recorded that for the last five years, the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of the third quarterly assessment of the grade 10 learners

of Gasan District has been low. The least mastered competencies were also noted. The researcher tailored the content to meet the learners' needs and level of understanding.

The researcher also ensured that the content was aligned with the relevant curriculum standards or learning outcomes to develop a module covering what is required for the grade 10 learners in the third quarter. All available content was reviewed, and unnecessary or tangential information was filtered out, keeping the focus on key concepts and principles that are directly relevant to the learning objectives. Each lesson in the module reflects the most important aspects of what is being taught.

The researcher also utilized frameworks such as Bloom's taxonomy to ensure that the selected content covers various levels of cognitive complexity, from basic understanding to higher-order thinking skills such as analysis and evaluation. Complex topics were broken down into smaller, more manageable, and easier-to-understand topics. Information was presented in a structured manner that facilitates understanding and retention. Different topics are presented accurately and precisely with a variety of supplementary activities. Ideas, concepts, and points presented are well-expressed.

The study of Omer et al (2001) stated that a module can be organized if it is constructed in logical ways by the nature of the lesson and the characteristics of the students it is intended for, such as from simple to complex, from known to unknown, from facts and fragmented knowledge to laws and comprehensive relationships, from the whole to the part, and from the ancient to the contemporary, which are arranged logically and sequentially.

Learning experiences with the developed module are enhanced by including visual aids such as diagrams, charts, and illustrations. Visual presentations presented in the module will help clarify complex concepts and improve comprehension among learners. The researcher also includes real-life examples and applications to demonstrate how the content is relevant and applicable in practical contexts. This helps learners connect theoretical knowledge to practical situations. The researcher reviewed and refined the module based on feedback from the teacher-respondent. The contents are adjusted to improve relevance, clarity, and effectiveness in achieving the learning objectives.

3. Selection of the language used

Several factors were considered by the researcher when selecting the appropriate language for crafting the module. These include the target audience, subject matter, and context.

The researcher researched the demographics, language proficiency, and cultural background of grade 10 learners to determine the language they were most comfortable with.

The language used in the module is designed to be accessible to the learners. The researcher avoided overly technical or academic language, ensuring the vocabulary and

instructions suited the learners' age and educational background. The instructions are presented in a clear, unambiguous, and easy-to-follow manner, enhancing the learners' comprehension of the module's content.

The language used supports the learning objectives. The researcher ensured that the language chosen communicates and engages learners effectively. The researcher sees to it that words are correctly used. The module is accompanied by clear and specific directions for their use. The lessons are presented in sentences and paragraphs that are grammatically correct.

The researcher also considered localization, which involves adapting the content linguistically and culturally to make it more relevant and understandable to the learners.

The researcher was able to gather and seek feedback from the teacher-respondents as evaluators of the developed module. This helped the researcher assess whether the language used resonates with learners and effectively communicates the content. The researcher made sure that consistency was maintained throughout the module in terms of terminology, style, and tone to avoid confusion and enhance learning continuity.

4. Development of assessment and evaluation activities

Developing assessment and evaluation activities for the module involved careful consideration of the learning objectives, content, and the learners' needs. The researcher clearly defined what the learners should achieve by the end of the lesson, and learning objectives or outcomes guided the researcher in the developing assessment and evaluation activities.

Knowing the learners' backgrounds, knowledge levels, and preferences helps the researcher tailor assessment activities to their needs and ensure they are engaging and relevant.

The researcher carefully considers appropriate assessment methods based on the learning objectives and the nature of the content. Assessment and evaluation activities are carefully designed to measure the intended learning outcomes. The researcher ensures that each assessment item is related to specific learning objectives. The module has a provision for self-assessment.

The researcher also provided clear instructions for assessment and evaluation activities. The purpose of each assessment activity and detailed instructions on how to do and complete it are stated clearly. These include information on the evaluation criteria and any relevant resources or materials.

The researcher ensured that assessment and evaluation items measure higher-order thinking skills, improving understanding and retention of the content.

Assessment activities are created with inclusive features that cater to diverse learning needs, including those who have learning difficulties. The test items are written carefully to ensure that learners can understand them. Moreover, the answer to one item provides a clue to the answer to another item.

With feedback from the teacher-respondent to the developed module, the researcher revised and refined assessment strategies as needed.

5. Selection of references from available teaching and learning sources

Though there are a limited number of available teaching and learning resources and materials for Grade 10, these resources are great sources and references used by the researcher in developing the module in Combinatorics and Probability.

In planning and crafting the module, thoughtful analysis of factors affecting the quality of teaching and learning was done. Such factors are problems and needs of the current curriculum and resources used in teaching. Content coverage of teaching materials and resources available are broad and general. Some are with abstract concepts. Some are experimental in nature and with research-based lessons. Some contents need prior knowledge to be understood. These identified gaps were taken into consideration in the process of structuring learning into the module to suit learning conditions.

The most important topics are determined for achieving the learning objectives. The researcher identified the core concepts and information essential for understanding the subject matter, which will be the module's focus. The developed module is more specific and comes with step-by-step procedure or solution to a given task or problem for learners to easily understand the topics discussed in the module.

Authors and their ideas from the resources used to develop the module in Combinatorics and Probability were properly cited and given credits to acknowledge the contribution of other writers and researchers in the developed module.

The researcher used the following resources, cited in APA format, as references in the developed module:

Callanta, Melvin, Canonigo, Allan, Chua, Arnaldo, Cruz, Jerry, Esparrago, Mirla, Garcia, Elino, Magnaye, Aries, Orines, Fernando, Perez, Rowena and Concepcion Ternida. *Mathematics Grade 10 Learner's*. Pasig: Department of Education, 2015

Oronce, Orlando, and Marilyn Mendoza. *E-Math 10*. Manila: Rex Bookstore, Inc., 2017.

Torio, Von, Ibanez, Jean, and Tiamzon, Ernan. *Smart in Math 10*. Quezon City. Isa-Jecho Publishing, Inc., 2018

6. Time frame of development

It took the researcher almost a year to complete the process of development and validation of the module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. Table 3 below shows the time frame of the module development.

Table 3.
Time frame of Module Development

Time	Activity
July 2023 to September 2023	Development and crafting of the module
October 2023	Distribution of the pre-crafted module and survey checklist to the respondents for evaluation
November 2023	Retrieval of the survey checklist
December 2023 to January 2024	Revision and editing of the Developed Module based on feedback of the respondents
February 2024 to March 2024	Pilot testing of the Developed Module

In July 2023, the researcher started the development of the module. The lack of teaching resources and learning materials for Combinatorics and Probability and the low mean percentage score in the third quarter in Mathematics 10 were the reasons which made the researcher conceptualize the development of the module.

Even before the pandemic in 2020, the Philippines faced challenges in mathematics education. The Philippines has consistently performed poorly in international mathematics large-scale assessments.

Meanwhile, Combinatorics is a mathematical topic considered challenging to teach and learn according to the study of Mashiach et al (2004), and Probability is unintuitive and difficult according to Spiegelhalter (2011). These support the study of Capuno et al (2019) saying Mathematics is challenging for Filipino students. That is why there is a need to design and develop the material to help Grade 10 learners understand the concept of Combinatorics and Probability.

From July to September 2023, the researcher developed and crafted the module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. ADDIE model was adapted and utilized in the development and validation of the module. The module's goals, target audience, and resources were analyzed in the analysis phase. In the design phase, essential content, objectives, and strategies aligned with the instructional goals were selected and designed. The development phase includes developing objectives, selecting essential content, determining the language used, and developing assessment and evaluation activities.

Before the distribution of the pre-crafted module to the respondents (teacher-validators) in October 2023, the researcher seek approval to conduct the study. First, the researcher sent a request letter to Dr. Lynn G. Mendoza, the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Marinduque, through the HR Office, asking permission to conduct the study in the five (5) public high schools in Gasan District through the distribution of survey questionnaires. The researcher also asked permission through a letter from Mr. Gueller Dee V. Salazar to adapt the instrument he used in his 2018 study to validate a developed module. Upon granting the researcher's request to adopt the research instrument used by Salazar (2018) and the approval of the Division Superintendent of Marinduque, the researcher printed a copy of the survey form and submitted it to the school district Supervisor of Gasan, Dr. Elvin C Perlas. The printed copy of the survey and consent forms were then personally distributed to the respondents. The researcher went to five (5) public high schools in Gasan District.

In November 2023, the researcher collected the completed survey questionnaires at the principal's respective office, and then the researcher consolidated the data. The researcher also did in-person interviews to validate the data gathered through the survey. After retrieving and collecting all the data needed, it was encoded, collated, organized, and statistically treated using the appropriate statistical tools. Results were considered by the researcher in module revision and development.

After analyzing the respondents' results, comments, and suggestions, the study concluded that the developed module is very much valid. Based on the feedback received, the researcher revised certain parts of the module to transform it into a valuable learning resource for grade 10 students from December 2023 to January 2024.

From February to March 2024, the final copy was implemented in the teaching-learning process using 30 students in Bangbang National High School. The researcher utilized the results of pretest and posttest administered to appraise the effect of the developed module on the learners' performance for the whole third quarter of the school year 2023-2024.

7. Development of cover page and packaging

According to evolutionary psychology, judging a book by its cover page is an inherent human trait based on survival, so first impressions matter immensely. Therefore, when designing a cover page for the development of a learning material, a captivating cover page is vital for making an expression. The cover page sets the tone of the content. It hints at what the content is about and is the first thing the reader is confronted with.

The researcher considered many elements to have a good and attractive design of the cover page of the developed module. The contrast, balance, emphasis, proportion, hierarchy, repetition, rhythm, pattern, white space, variety and unit.

The purpose of the content and the target audience of the module are considered by the researcher to create stand-out cover page and packaging. The questions "What am I creating and who is it for?", "What message do I want to convey?", and "Who am I

trying to reach?” are considered and answered by the researcher in creating the cover page of the developed module.

To create a compelling cover page and packaging, it’s essential to include a vital visual element that aligns with the theme of the content. The researcher chose a visual element that grabs attention without overwhelming the viewers, a captivating image, or an eye-catching graphic about the module. The researcher wanted to capture the learners’ attention but not overwhelm them. Using too many different types of visuals on the same page are avoided to maintain a clean or organized look. The researcher chose a harmonious color palette that aligns with the purpose of the module, and target audience – the Grade 10 learners

The researcher experimented with different lay-outs and arrangements of the visuals and illustrations in the cover page of the developed module to find the perfect balance which will captivate the learners’ attention. A balanced composition ensures that the cover page looks visually appealing and professional.

Level of Validity of the Developed Module

The draft of the module was written and printed. The developed module was distributed to the evaluators/validators of the module, the secondary school mathematics teachers, and master teachers teaching Mathematics 10 Third quarter, Combinatorics and Probability topics in Gasan District. Using the survey checklist adapted from the validated evaluation instrument Salazar (2018) used, the module was assessed and evaluated according to the four criteria: the lesson’s objectives, essential content, the language used, and assessment and evaluation activities. Each criterion had quantifying statements on which the evaluators based their assessment of the module.

Table 4.
Rating on the Characteristics of the Specific Objectives of the Developed Module

Indicators	Frequency					Average	D	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. Each lesson in the module is accompanied by specific objectives.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
2. The words used in the objectives are clear and easily understood.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
3. The specific objectives are realistic.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
4. The objectives are measurable	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
5. The specific objectives are attainable within specified time limit.	2	3	0	0	0	4.40	Excellent	VMV

Composite Mean	4.80	Excellent	VMV
Legend:			
1.00 – 1.79	<i>poor</i>		<i>not valid (NV)</i>
1.80 – 2.59	<i>fair</i>		<i>less valid (LV)</i>
2.60 – 3.39	<i>satisfactory</i>		<i>moderately valid (ModV)</i>
3.40 – 4.19	<i>very satisfactory</i>		<i>much valid (MV)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	<i>excellent</i>		<i>very much valid (VMV)</i>
<i>D</i>	<i>Description</i>		
<i>DI</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>		

Table 4 presents the ratings given by the mathematics teachers and master teachers on the specific objectives of the module.

The specific objectives of each lesson in the module were rated very much valid, with a composite mean of 4.80. Evaluators gave the highest average rating of 5.0, considering that the module is accompanied by specific objectives that are clear and easily understood, realistic, measurable, and attainable within a specific time limit.

Specific objectives accompany each lesson in the module. Defined learning goals are broken down into smaller, more manageable learning objectives describing the knowledge, skills, or attitudes the learners should gain.

The words used in the objectives are clear and easily understood. Each learning objective uses precise, actionable verbs describing observable behaviors. Action verbs such as analyze, evaluate, synthesize, and apply indicate the level of cognitive engagement required of learners. Vague or ambiguous language that can lead to confusion is avoided.

The learning objectives are sequenced in a logical order that allows for progression and coherence, starting with foundational concepts and skills and moving on to more advanced topics.

The objectives are realistic, measurable, and attainable within the specified time limit. Each objective communicates precisely what learners are expected to accomplish within the time.

As Donnelly and Fitzmaurice (2005) noted in their study, the module must be accompanied by distinct learning objectives so that learners are aware of what they must do after engaging in the learning process.

Table 5.
Rating on the Content of the Module

Indicators	Frequency					Average	D	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. Each lesson reflects the most important aspects of what is being taught.	3	2	0	0	0	4.60	Excellent	VMV
2. The lessons are presented at a pace that allows for reflection and review.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
3. There is adequate provision for supplementary activities/exercises.	3	2	0	0	0	4.60	Excellent	VMV
4. The content leads to the attainment of the objectives.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
5. There is adequate presentation/discussion of content.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
6. The information about the different topics is accurate and precise.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
7. There is variety of supplementary activities	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
8. The ideas, concepts, and points presented are well-expressed.	4	0	1	0	0	4.60	Excellent	VMV
9. The examples presented are current, accurate, and defensible.	2	3	0	0	0	4.40	Excellent	VMV
10. The lessons are aligned on the curriculum.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
Composite Mean						4.74	Excellent	VMV

Legend:

1.00 – 1.79	<i>poor</i>	<i>not valid (NV)</i>
1.80 – 2.59	<i>fair</i>	<i>less valid (LV)</i>
2.60 – 3.39	<i>satisfactory</i>	<i>moderately valid (ModV)</i>
3.40 – 4.19	<i>very satisfactory</i>	<i>much valid (MV)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	<i>excellent</i>	<i>very much valid (VMV)</i>
D	<i>Description</i>	
DI	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	

Table 5 provides the evaluators' rating of the content of the module. The module's content was rated using the ten (10) specific criteria with a composite mean of 4.74, which is very much valid. Based on the rating, it can be noted that each lesson reflects the most important aspects of what is being taught. Also, the lessons in the module are presented at a pace that allows for reflection and review. That is why the evaluators' highest rating was five (5) on that specific criterion. The module's contents also lead to attaining the objectives, and there is an adequate presentation and discussion of content. The

module's content is aligned with the relevant curriculum standards or learning outcomes covering the topics required for Grade 10 learners in the third quarter.

The content leads to the attainment of the objectives. In the study conducted by Roman (2016), it was emphasized that the content contributes to the assessment of the module's validity.

The module enriches learning experiences by incorporating visual aids such as diagrams, charts, and illustrations. These visual presentations serve a practical purpose, clarifying complex concepts and enhancing comprehension among learners. Real-life examples and applications demonstrate the relevance and applicability of the content in practical contexts, ensuring that learners can apply their knowledge effectively.

Lai and Neuby (2012) found that the quality of the graphics presented in a module can affect how it is interpreted, and the benefits derived from using it. Pictures and other visual aids decrease the need for extended textual descriptions. Graphics can enhance understanding, inference, prospective discovery, and learner motivation.

Table 6.
Rating on the Language Used in the Module

Indicators	Frequency					Average	D	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The words used in the module are correctly used.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
2. The module is accompanied by clear and specific directions for their use.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
3. The vocabulary used is suitable to the reading and understanding level of students to whom the modules are intended.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
4. Instructions to the students are clear, unambiguous, and easy to follow.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
5. The lessons are presented in paragraph/sentences that are grammatically correct.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
Composite Mean						4.84	Excellent	VMV

Legend:

1.00 – 1.79	poor	not valid (NV)
1.80 – 2.59	fair	less valid (LV)
2.60 – 3.39	satisfactory	moderately valid (ModV)
3.40 – 4.19	very satisfactory	much valid (MV)
4.20 – 5.00	excellent	very much valid (VMV)
D	Description	
DI	Descriptive Interpretation	

Table 6 shows the rating of the mathematics teachers and mathematics teachers on the language used in the module.

The language usage of the module has a composite mean of 4.84. This means that the choice of words is very much valid and appropriate to the learners' reading ability and accompanied by clear and specific directions for their use.

The language used in the module is accessible to the learners, meaning they are familiar with the words used. Words used in the module can be easily understood by the learners. There are no technical or academic languages that are hard to understand.

Similarly, the level of readability of words is appropriate to the learners' age and educational background. The vocabulary used suits the reading and understanding level of learners to whom the module is intended. Instructions to the students are clear, unambiguous, and easy to follow. Clear instructions make learners do and finish the task accurately and precisely.

The language used supports the module's learning objectives. Chosen language effectively communicates concepts and engages learners. Words in the module are used correctly. The lessons are presented in paragraphs and sentences that are grammatically correct.

When creating a concise and clear concept, language, ideas, and structure for the module, consideration must be given to the learner's learning capacities, preferences, and degree of knowledge. According to Salazar (2018), in his study, the module's clarity must be given with clear information and language to facilitate learning.

Table 7.
Rating on the Assessment and Evaluation Activities in the Module

Indicators	Frequency					Average	D	DI
	5	4	3	2	1			
1. The module has provision for self-assessment.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
2. The items help increase understanding and retention of the content.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
3. The items focus on important objectives and content of the lessons.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
4. The items in the evaluation are congruent to the specific objectives.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
5. There are items which measure higher thinking skills.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV

6. The items are grammatically correct.	5	0	0	0	0	5.00	Excellent	VMV
7. The items are arranged from easy to difficult.	3	2	0	0	0	4.60	Excellent	VMV
8. The test items are written at a level that students can understand.	3	2	0	0	0	4.60	Excellent	VMV
9. The answer to one item furnishes or gives clue to the answer in another item.	3	1	1	0	0	4.40	Excellent	VMV
10. The items cover the important competencies to be developed.	4	1	0	0	0	4.80	Excellent	VMV
Composite Mean						4.82	Excellent	VMV

Legend:

1.00 – 1.79	<i>poor</i>	<i>not valid (NV)</i>
1.80 – 2.59	<i>fair</i>	<i>less valid (LV)</i>
2.60 – 3.39	<i>satisfactory</i>	<i>moderately valid (ModV)</i>
3.40 – 4.19	<i>very satisfactory</i>	<i>much valid (MV)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	<i>excellent</i>	<i>very much valid (VMV)</i>
<i>D</i>	<i>Description</i>	
<i>DI</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	

Table 7 presents the rating given by the mathematics teachers and master teachers on the assessment and evaluation activities in the module.

The evaluation format gained a composite mean of 4.82, meaning the set of assessment tools was very much valid. The evaluation tools used in the developed module measure what is supposed to be measured.

Assessment methods are appropriate based on the learning objectives and the nature of the content. Assessment activities directly measure the intended learning outcomes. Each assessment item is related to specific learning objectives. Instructions for each assessment and evaluation activity are provided clearly. The purpose of each assessment activity and detailed instructions on how to do and complete the task are clearly stated.

Assessment and evaluation items help increase understanding and retention of the content. Some items measure higher-order thinking skills. The items are grammatically correct. The items are arranged from easy to complex. Considering accessibility and inclusivity in the assessment, assessment activities are made accessible to all learners, including those with learning disabilities or diverse learning needs. Answers to one item furnishes or gives clues to the answer in another item. The test items are written carefully at a level that learners can understand. Also, items in the assessment and evaluation activities of the developed module cover the essential competencies to be developed by learners. Items focus on important objectives of the lessons.

According to Heramil (2016), a self-learning module has been designed to aid learners who cannot attend individual or group education sessions. This module provides learning activities and assessment and evaluation of the students, enabling learners to work independently at their own pace rather than the group's pace, which can either be too fast or too slow for some learners.

Result of the Validation of the Developed Module

Table 8.

Summary Result of Rating on the Validation of the Developed Module

Indicators	Mean	D	DI
I. Characteristics of the specific objectives of the module	4.80	Excellent	VMV
II. Characteristics of the content of the module	4.74	Excellent	VMV
III. Characteristics of the language used	4.84	Excellent	VMV
IV. Characteristics of evaluation activities	4.82	Excellent	VMV
Average Weighted Mean	4.80	Excellent	VMV

Legend:

1.00 – 1.79	<i>poor</i>	<i>not valid (NV)</i>
1.80 – 2.59	<i>fair</i>	<i>less valid (LV)</i>
2.60 – 3.39	<i>satisfactory</i>	<i>moderately valid (ModV)</i>
3.40 – 4.19	<i>very satisfactory</i>	<i>much valid (MV)</i>
4.20 – 5.00	<i>excellent</i>	<i>very much valid (VMV)</i>
D	<i>Description</i>	
DI	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>	

Table 8 presents the rating summary result on the developed module's validation. The module developed by the researcher is very much valid, as reflected by the ratings of the evaluators—the mathematics teachers and the master teachers of Gasan District. After thorough analysis and computation of the survey checklist result used as the research instrument to evaluate the developed module, the average weighted mean of 4.80, which is very much valid, is the general experts' feedback on the developed module.

The evaluation result confirmed that the output module is very much valid. Though there are minor issues, comments, feedback, and suggestions by the validators which need to be considered. In general, the developed module is near to a perfect learning resource that will provide the teachers and learners with what is needed for the teaching and learning process, a module that will help create self-phase learning and that will significantly enhance the mathematical skills of students, potentially transforming their academic journey. The module may serve as a relevant learning resource that may increase the potential in mathematical skills through reasoning and analogy aligned with the DepEd curriculum and content standards.

Comments, Feedback, and Suggestions of the Validators to help Enhance the Developed Module

- There should be an introduction or preface about the topic or lesson for the week. This may include but is not limited to the importance of the lesson as to why it is essential to teach and learn. While the content itself is most important, a strong introduction can engage learners, provide context, and outline what learners are going to learn. Introductions, even brief ones, can make a huge difference for the learners' learning experience. A strong introduction can hook learners and pique their interests (Amanda, 2023).
- There should be a table of content so that lessons will be seen easily. A table of contents is a page or section of books, modules, and other learning materials that lists the chapters or sections of the material and their corresponding page number. The table of contents serves two purposes: 1). It gives users an overview of the document's contents and organization, and 2). It allows readers to go directly to a specific section of a document.
- In the discussion part of the lesson in the module, the writer / researcher may apply the 3E's (Engage, Elaborate, and Evaluate).

Engage. The part or section of the module which provides activity / activities to gain an understanding of the students' prior knowledge and identify knowledge gaps if there is. This part also fosters an interest in the upcoming concepts so that students will be ready to learn.

Elaborate. This phase focuses on giving students space to apply what they've learned. This helps them to develop a deeper understanding of the lesson.

Evaluate. It is in this phase of the module which provides activity / activities to see whether learners have a complete grasp of the core concepts discussed.

- Examples provided in each of the lessons in the developed module should be localized and contextualized especially in the problem-solving part of the lesson. Localization and contextualization are crucial in education because these ensure that learning materials are accessible and relevant to students across different linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Essential content should be aligned with local languages, customs, and cultural norms.

The Enhanced Module in Combinatorics and Probability

As a result of the validation and series of revision, the enhanced module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners can be a potential learning material that can help assist teachers in presenting lessons in Combinatorics and Probability.

The enhanced module is packed wholly and systematically with a set of planned learning experiences inside designed to help students to comprehend specific learning goals and competencies. This module is different from other existing modules in Mathematics because examples provided in the module are localized and contextualized making them to be easily understood by learners.

Earlier studies show how instructional materials can assist teachers in presenting their lesson logically and sequentially to the learners (Isola, 2010), as supported by Abdu-Raheem (2014), who showed in his study how instructional materials aid explanations and make the learning of subject matter understandable to learners during the teaching-learning process.

Pretest and Posttest Analysis Using the Developed Module

The validated copy of the module in Combinatorics and Probability was pilot tested among the 30 grade 10 learners. Learner's performance was determined by calculating the percentage of students who showed improvement in their scores after they underwent learning through the module using pretest and posttest assessments. The difference in mean percentage score (MPS) which is equal to 46.40 indicates that the learners significantly acquired knowledge in the lessons. This further implies that the utilization of the developed module led students to have a better performance.

Furthermore, the utilization of the material not only enhanced comprehension and knowledge but also piqued the student's interest in the subject as observed during the pilot testing. It was clear that students were actively engaged in the learning process with the teacher acting as a facilitator (Raman, 2006). The developed module likely supports independent learning. This aligns with Naval (2014), in his research, indicating that students tend to engage with modules at their preferred times, and this particular module made them to be interested in learning. Consequently, students exhibited high concentration due to the learner-centered exercises included in the module (Lea, 2003).

The increase in MPS from the pretest to posttest indicates that positive learning occurred. The posttest scores reflect that 45 out of 50 items were correctly answered by the learners with an MPS of 89.74. The analysis results displayed in Table 9 show that the majority of the students performed well in the subject. Posttest rating reveals that 87% of the learners had an outstanding rating and 13% had very satisfactory rating.

Table 9.*Performance of Learners Using the Result of Pretest and Posttest Analysis*

Difference in MPS of Pretest and Posttest										
Type of Test	No. of Cases	No. of Items	HPS	LPS	HSO	LSO	Mean	MPS	SD	Difference in MPS (Posttest – Pretest)
Pretest	30	50	50	0	35	11	21.67	43.34	6.12	46.40
Posttest	30	50	50	0	50	38	44.87	89.74	2.97	

Learner Progress and Achievement in Pretest and Posttest						
Descriptors	Grading Scale	Remarks	Pretest		Posttest	
			No. of Learners	%	No. of Learners	%
Outstanding	90 – 100	Passed	0	0%	26	87%
Very Satisfactory	85 – 89	Passed	0	%	4	13%
Satisfactory	80 – 84	Passed	1	3%	0	0%
Fairly Satisfactory	75 – 79	Passed	1	3%	0	0%
Did not meet Expectations	Below 75	Failed	28	94%	0	0%
Total			30	100%	30	100%

Note: Computation of Learners' Progress and Achievement in Pretest and Posttest was based on DepEd Order No. 8 s. 2015

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

This study aimed to develop and validate a module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. The lack of teaching resources and learning materials for Combinatorics and Probability and the low mean percentage score in the third quarterly assessment of the subject mentioned above are the existing problems from the current curriculum of the Department of Education. These are the reasons that made the researcher conceptualize the development of the module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. The researcher used the ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) model to develop the module.

The module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners was developed in terms of:

- Development of the intended learning outcomes

Learning goals are defined considering the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) prescribed by the Department of Education (DepEd). These learning goals were broken down into smaller, more manageable objectives aligned with the curriculum standards and overall goals. These learning outcomes/objectives were specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART).

- Selection of the essential content

The core concepts and information essential for understanding the subject matter were identified and will be the module's focus. The topics/lessons under Mathematics 10 Combinatorics and Probability for Quarter 3 are listed per module every week, Module 1 to Module 10, with K to 12 curriculum guide codes. These are as follows:

- Module 1 – Week 1: Illustrating Permutations of Objects (M10SP-IIIa-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Permutation of Distinct Objects
 - Lesson 2: Illustrating Permutation of Non-Distinct Objects
 - Lesson 3: Illustrating Circular Permutation of Objects
- Module 2 – Week 2: Solving Problems involving Permutations of Objects (M10SP-IIIb-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving Problems involving Permutations of Objects
- Module 3 – Week 3: Illustrating Combinations of Objects (M10SP-IIIc-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Combinations of Objects
 - Lesson 2: Differentiating Permutation and Combination
- Module 4 – Week 4: Combination of n Objects Taken r at a Time (M10SP-IIIc-2)
 - Lesson 1: Combination of n objects taken r at a time
- Module 5 – Week 5: Solving Problems involving Permutations and Combinations (M10SP-IIId-e-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving Problems involving Permutations and Combinations
- Module 6 – Week 6: Events, and Union and Intersection of Events (M10SP-IIIf-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Different Types of Events
 - Lesson 2: Illustrating Union, and Intersection of Events
- Module 7 – Week 7: Probability of The Union of Two Events (M10SP-IIIg-1)
 - Lesson 1: Probability of The Union of Two Events
- Module 8 – Week 8: Solving the Probability of $A \cup B$ (M10SP-IIIg-h-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving the Probability of $A \cup B$
- Module 9 – Week 9: Illustrating Mutually Exclusive Events (M10SP-IIIf-i-1)
 - Lesson 1: Illustrating Mutually Exclusive Events
- Module 10 – Week 10: Solving Problems involving Probabilities (M10SP-IIIj-1)
 - Lesson 1: Solving the Probability of Independent Events and Dependent Events
 - Lesson 2: Solving Conditional Probability

Learners' backgrounds, prior knowledge, and learning preferences were considered. The content is aligned with the curriculum standards and learning outcomes. The content covers levels of cognitive complexity, from basic understanding to higher-order thinking skills. Different topics are presented accurately and precisely with a variety of supplementary materials. Ideas, concepts, and points presented are well-expressed.

The content and learning experiences were enhanced by visual aids such as illustrations, diagrams, and charts, which help clarify complex concepts and improve comprehension.

- Selection of the language used

The vocabulary used is suitable for the reading and understanding level of the learners to whom the modules are intended. The instructions are clear, unambiguous, and easy to follow. The language used supports the learning objectives. The language chosen communicates and engages learners effectively. The module uses correct words. It is accompanied by clear and specific directions for its use. The lessons are presented in sentences and paragraphs that are grammatically correct.

- Development of the assessment and evaluation activities

Assessment activities are accessible to all learners, including those with learning difficulties or diverse learning needs. Test items are carefully written at a level that learners can understand. The assessment and evaluation items help increase understanding and retention of the content. Items measure higher-order thinking skills. The answer to one item furnishes or gives a clue to the answer to another item.

- Selection of references from available teaching and learning sources

Though there are a limited number of available teaching and learning resources and materials for Grade 10, these resources are great sources and references used by the researcher in developing the module in Combinatorics and Probability. The most important topics are determined for achieving the learning objectives. The researcher identified the core concepts and information essential for understanding the subject matter, which will be the module's focus. Authors and their ideas from the resources used to develop the module in Combinatorics and Probability were properly cited and given credits to acknowledge the contribution of other writers and researchers in the developed module.

- Time frame of the development

- ✓ July 2023 to September 2023 – Development and crafting of the module
- ✓ October 2023 – Distribution of the pre-crafted module and survey checklist to the respondents for evaluation
- ✓ November 2023 – Retrieval of the survey checklist
- ✓ December 2023 to January 2024 – Revision and editing of the Developed Module based on feedback of the respondents
- ✓ February 2024 to March 2024 – Pilot testing of the Developed Module

- Development of cover page and packaging

The researcher experimented with different lay-outs and arrangements of the visuals and illustrations in the cover page of the developed module to find the perfect balance which will captivate the learners' attention. A balanced composition ensures that the cover page looks visually appealing and professional.

The draft of the module was written, printed, and validated. The module was assessed and evaluated in four general categories with quantifying statements on which

the validators based their module assessment. The four categories with the result are as follows:

- specific objectives of each lesson in the module with a mean of 4.8,
- content of the module with a mean of 4.74,
- language used with a mean of 4.84, and
- assessment and evaluation activities with a mean of 4.82.

The result revealed that the developed module was considered very much valid, with an average weighted mean of 4.8. Comments, feedback, and suggestions from the validators are noted and taken into consideration to enhance the module.

Positive learning was determined by computing the percentage of students who showed improvement in their scores after they underwent learning through the module. The mean percentage score of students' pretest and posttest were compared and a difference of 46.40 shows that the students significantly improved their performance in the subject. There were 87% and 13% of learners who obtained outstanding rating and very satisfactory rating in posttest respectively. The mean score of the pilot students is 44.87.

The developed module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners is a potential learning resource that can be used to teach Grade 10 Combinatorics and Probability topics in Quarter 3.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered using the standardized module evaluation checklist adapted from a validated scholarly work published as material for development and validation, it can be concluded that the developed module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners is very much valid. The developed module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners is a potential learning resource that can be used in teaching Grade 10 Mathematics Combinatorics and Probability topics in the third quarter.

Pilot-testing verified these conclusions through an obtained difference of 46.40 in the MPS using the pretest-posttest analysis. This is supported by the performance of 87% of students who obtained an outstanding rating and 13% of students who obtained a very satisfactory rating.

Indeed, the developed module can provide teachers and learners with what is needed to teach and learn Combinatorics and Probability. It can help learners create self-phase learning and enhance their mathematical skills. The module may serve as a relevant learning resource that can increase the learners' potential in mathematical skills through reasoning and analogy aligned with the DepEd curriculum and content standards.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The respondents/validators of the developed module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners are the mathematics teachers and master teachers in Gasan District who are teaching Mathematics 10, specifically Combinatorics and Probability. To increase the developed module's validity, the researcher highly suggests testing the module into a series of evaluations and assessments by a more significant number of evaluators and widening the scope of the study. Subjecting the developed module to experts in module writing and publication will also increase its validity.
2. This study mainly focused on the development and validation of the module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. The questionnaire, in checklist form adapted from the validated evaluation instrument used by other researchers, was distributed among the Mathematics teachers and master teachers in Gasan District who are teaching Mathematics 10, specifically Combinatorics and Probability. They are the validators of the developed module. For further refinement, the researcher recommends also considering students' evaluation if one will conduct development and validation of the module to identify learners' feedback after using the module.
3. For further study, the researcher also recommends testing the developed module's effectiveness by letting the grade 10 learners from other school use the module to learn the lesson on Combinatorics and Probability for the third quarter in Mathematics 10 to increase its validity.
4. The developed module in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners is a potential learning resource that can be used in teaching Grade 10 Combinatorics and Probability topics in the third quarter. The developed module can provide the teachers and learners with what is needed in teaching and learning Combinatorics and Probability. This module can help learners create self-phase learning and enhance their mathematical skills. When given the opportunity to use the module as a reference, researchers may continue to elaborate and improve the existing content of Combinatorics and Probability. Contextualization and localization of examples are encouraged for the content of the module.
5. The need for teaching resources in Mathematics lessons, such as Combinatorics and Probability topics, is one of the reasons why the researcher conceptualizes developing and validating modules in Combinatorics and Probability for Grade 10 learners. The government may allocate funds for this kind of study about the development and validation of modules because such studies will produce potential learning modules and materials to help teachers in teaching.

6. Essentially, the success of the module may depend on the competence, enthusiasm, and confidence of the Mathematics teacher and the ability of the students in making use of the learning activities provided.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

It is true that developing and crafting a module is a process that requires time, commitment, and a thoughtful, systematic approach.

This study involved human participation for the evaluation of the developed module and its impact on the performance of the learners. Several considerations for this undertaking are truly necessary for the purpose of ensuring the privacy as well as the security of the participants. These concerns were identified in advance so as to prevent future problems that would arise during the research process. Among the significant issues which were considered include consent, confidentiality, and data protection.

During the conduct of the study, survey forms and interview methods were drafted in a very clear and concise manner to prevent confusion. Participants in this research were given ample time to respond to the survey checklist to avoid errors and inaccuracies in their answers. The respondents were also given a waiver and information that they do not wish to disclose. The respondents' cooperation was eagerly sought after. They were assured that the data gathered would be treated with strict confidence. These were done with the hope that this would promote trust between the researcher and the respondents.

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